

Organizational Forms of Work with Gifted Students in Foreign Language Classes

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Abstract:

One of the strategic directions of development of national education is support of talented and gifted youth. Creation of conditions ensuring identification and development of gifted students, realization of their potential opportunities is one of the priority social tasks of modern society. Increased interest in problems of giftedness is dictated by the social order of society and contributes to intensive growth of researches in this area. The article considers problems of organizational forms of work with gifted students in foreign language classes.

Keywords: Linguistic giftedness, students, organization, foreign language, cognitive activity, motivation.

Introduction:

Every year the education system improves. New methods and approaches to teaching students appear. This is especially true for learning languages, since immersing a student in the paradigm of a foreign language requires great efforts to increase the productivity of this process. However, modern students are surrounded by such a large flow of information that some of them learn to perceive foreign languages from a young age and are considered gifted, having great success in this subject at school. This means that they need a special approach so as not to destroy the desire to learn the language, not to allow existing skills to degrade.

Literature review:

A huge contribution to the development of the theory of giftedness was made by the research of N.S. Leites. By giftedness he understands the totality of all the abilities of the individual and its specific properties, revealed in the “peculiarities of mastering skills, in the ability to adequately respond to a situation, in the creative nature of achievements”. The researcher distinguishes two

types of giftedness: “child prodigy”, characterized by accelerated mental development and distinguished by increased mental activity, and “non-child prodigy”, which involves gradual development and slow increase in abilities, the heyday of which occurs not at an early, but at a later age. Analyzing age sensitivity in childhood, N.S. Leites considers those mental characteristics that create the “potential” of the child, special prerequisites for his further development, and proposes to distinguish three categories of capable children of preschool and primary school age:

1. children with early development of intelligence;
2. children with a clear manifestation of abilities in individual sciences and types of activities;
3. children with potential, not clearly expressed abilities. However, in the author's opinion, the term "giftedness" in relation to children is used conditionally, since it serves only to designate a "peculiar reality". The main characteristic of children's giftedness should be considered the age-related characteristics of the child, qualitatively distinguishing him from an adult and directly affecting the children's abilities [6, p. 139].

Giftedness is a systemic, developing throughout a person's life, mental quality that determines a person's ability to achieve higher and more outstanding results not only in one, but in a wide variety of activities compared to other people. Despite the considerable ambiguity of this term, it has nevertheless become very widespread in recent decades in psychology [5, p. 340].

Discussions:

Linguistic giftedness of students is “an increased level of ability for accelerated thinking processes in a foreign language, for active cognitive activity in the field of theory and history of language, for creativity in choosing methods of communication in a foreign language, for stable motivation in learning a language.”

The components of linguistic giftedness are “a sense of language,” “language guess or intuition,” “language and communication abilities,” “foreign language abilities.”

1. A sense of language is an emotional feeling of coherence/incoherence, harmony in language, understanding of the systemic properties of language that accompanies the process of generating and perceiving speech. This process occurs as a result of subconscious generalization of numerous speech acts [3, p. 472];
2. A sense of language is a phenomenon of intuitive language proficiency that manifests itself in understanding and using idiomatic, lexical, stylistic and other constructions even before the purposeful acquisition of the language in training. It is a generalization at the level of primary generalization without preliminary conscious isolation of the elements included in this generalization. It is formed as a result of spontaneous mastery of speech and basic cognitive operations. Provides control and assessment of the correctness and familiarity of language constructions [4, p.323].

Currently, the goals and objectives of education in universities and technical institutes are being adjusted. Currently, people with unconventional thinking, who are able to find new ways to solve certain problems and tasks, who are able to find a way out of the most difficult situations, are increasingly valued. Formulating the definition of giftedness, psychologist V. Stern cited this type of people as an example: "Mental giftedness is a general ability to consciously direct one's thinking to new requirements, is a general mental ability to adapt to new tasks and living conditions." Giftedness remains a mystery for most teachers and many parents [7]. However, for teachers, the most important thing is not so much the scientific basis of giftedness, but its real manifestations, methods of identification, development and socialization. Linguistic (language) giftedness manifests itself already in preschool age. At this stage, teachers develop students in a complex of five areas:

1. Development of sensory and motor functions;
2. Development of intellectual functions (thinking, memory, imagination, perception, attention and orientation in space and time);
3. Development of the emotional-volitional sphere and play activities;
4. Development of facial muscles;
5. Formation of harmonious personality traits.

American scientists John B. Carroll, Stanley Sapon identified four groups of special cognitive abilities that underlie the successful acquisition of a foreign language:

1. Phonetic coding ability - perception of the sounds of a foreign language and sound forms of words and expressions, their "coding" in long-term memory and reproduction when necessary.
2. Grammatical sensitivity - the ability to perceive grammatical relations in a foreign language and understand the role of grammar in the generation and translation of statements and sentences.
3. Mechanical associative memory (rote associational) - necessary for the acquisition of a large number of arbitrary connections between words and their meanings that must be acquired.
4. Inductive ability – general cognitive ability, the ability to see and derive rules that govern the formation of stimulus models. Thus, foreign language abilities are characterized by at least the level of cognitive abilities, verbal intelligence and the ability for productive and reproductive speech activity [2].

Giftedness of a student is understood as higher abilities and susceptibility to learning than his peers under equal conditions. At the same time, such students also demonstrate brighter manifestations of creativity. The task of the teacher is to notice, recognize talent and create favorable conditions for its development. It is known that creativity is a necessary condition for the further development of a student. Engaged in creative activities, the student begins to show interest in learning. As a result, he achieves higher academic results. A modern teacher should also think creatively, be a creative person. In fact, he should captivate and lead. In other words, such a teacher is called upon not only to prepare graduates with a good level of knowledge, but to develop and educate young people who are able to receive and apply new knowledge, who are able to create and implement projects, and who are socially mobile. The system of working with gifted students within the framework of the subject "Foreign Language" is determined by the extent to which the educational process ensures the development of students' creative abilities, namely through the organization of students' in-class and extracurricular activities.

The implementation of creating conditions for the development of a creative gifted personality should begin in the first or second year of study. The lesson is the basis of work with gifted students, but in this case, it requires a different composition, different content and a different organization of the educational and cognitive activities of students. We can say that an unconventional lesson is an organic combination of training, development and education. Students like unconventional lessons because they are creative and unusual, and most importantly - effective. But unconventional lessons should not be held too often, because they will become traditional and the level of effectiveness will decrease. In foreign language lessons in higher education institutions, the following are methodically highly effective, implementing unconventional forms of training, development and education of students:

The lesson is a virtual excursion, allows students to participate in various imaginary situations of intercultural communication. During the virtual excursion, they can visit a park, organizations of their specialization - banks, factories, joint ventures, another city or country. Students try

themselves in the role of a tourist, a tour guide, a manager, an economist, a resident of another country. In this way, not only the communicative task of the lesson is solved, but also fantasy, imaginative imagination, and the ability to transform into another image are developed.

When working with gifted students, it is necessary to use an interactive method. Creative tasks and projects form the basis of any interactive lesson. They give meaning to learning and motivate students. An unknown answer and the opportunity to find your own correct solution based on your personal experience and the experience of a friend provide an opportunity for the development of cooperation among all participants in the educational process.

Conclusion:

Thus, when working with linguistically gifted students, it is necessary to diversify their educational activities so that they develop a special interest in the area of activity in which their abilities and inclinations prevail; use non-traditional methods of work. The task of teachers is to help a gifted child find his or her own path of development so that the uniqueness and peculiarity of such a child does not disappear. However, in the modern world there is a growing tendency to increase the number of students who have a higher level of ability in foreign languages than others. This is explained by the growing flow of information that surrounds a child from childhood and the desire of many parents to raise their child to be at least bilingual. Teachers and specialists must take into account these facts of the shift in the paradigm of education to the area of languages and the need of a modern person for foreign communications. This is why the phenomenon of linguistic giftedness should be studied more than it has been studied now.

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